

Molecular Detection of Some Viral Gastroenteritis Which Transmitted by Food in Children from Wasit Province

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Abstract:

Aim of study to detect the viral causes of gastroenteritis in stool samples from children in Wasit province by Immunochromatographic test and molecular detection for *Rotavirus*, *Adenovirus* and *Norovirus*.

Materials and methods: In this study one hundred stool samples were collected from ill children (27 days-48 months in age) with GE symptoms. The samples were collected from many hospitals and health centers in Wasit province while fifty stool samples were collected from healthy children as a control group from two kindergartens. The patients' samples were categorized into eight

groups according to age of the children, following WHO recommendations 2009b. All samples were tested by Rapid Immunochromatographic test (RIT) and RT-qPCR with specific primers and probes

Results: RIT found that 31%, 1%, were positive to *Rotavirus*, *Adenovirus*, respectively and 0% for *Norovirus*. Importantly, also the same results for *Rotavirus* and *Adenovirus* seen by using RT-qPCR with specific primers and probes. In addition, the results showed that *Rotavirus* infection cases were higher in males than females, 56% and 44 %, respectively. Child age plays a significant role in *Rotavirus* infections. The results of this study showed that children aged (3-5 months) more likely to have *Rotavirus* infection (25.8 %) compared to other children. Diarrhea (100%) and vomiting (97.77%) were the most clinical symptoms of children who diagnosed with *Rotavirus* infections. This study investigated the most three common viral that cause GE infection in children in Wasit province and found that *Rotavirus* was the main cause of GE.

Keywords: *Rotavirus*, *Adenovirus*, *Norovirus*, RT-qPCR, Rapid Immunochromatographic test.

Introduction

Gastroenteritis (GE) is an inflammation of gastrointestinal tract which includes both stomach and intestine (Amandeep.,2010). Two billions cases of GE recorded in 2015 resulted in 1.3 million death globally (GBD 2015). It has

been found that the main causative agents of GE were viruses, bacteria and parasites (Freeman *et al.*,2017. Zbinden.2019), *Rotavirus*(RV) is the most common virus that cause GE in children under 5 years old and RV responsible for 5% of all child death yearly (Muendo,2018). In 2016 WHO estimated that globally 215000(19700-

23300) children death in 2013 due to *Rotavirus*, (2231) children in Iraq were infected with diarrhea died 990 of them infected with RV (WHO. Report Estimated rotavirus deaths for children under 5 years of age, 2013). *Rotavirus* considered as the most important cause of endemic severe diarrheal illness in infant and young children in the world, while *Adenovirus* was the second most important viral agent of endemic diarrheal illness of infants and young children in the world. *Norovirus* is considered as a noticeable cause of outbreaks with vomiting and diarrheal illness in older children and adults (Jawetz *et al.*,2016). In the United States, rotavirus is thought to cause less than 1% of all foodborne illness, with an estimated 15,433 cases of gastroenteritis and 34 hospitalizations being associated with foodborne rotavirus infections annually. Still, the economic burden of foodborne rotavirus disease is approximately \$18 million in direct health care costs. most foodborne rotavirus illness arises from contamination by an infected food handler. Thus, adherence to strict hygienic rules, along all levels of the farm-to-fork continuum, is essential to curtail rotavirus food contamination (Paul *et al.*,2013).

Rotavirus is a member of the Reoviridae family group A which are the main viral human pathogen (Schaeffer, *et al* : Sano *et al.* 2016). *Rotavirus* is a double strand RNA (dsRNA) with a genome that composes of 11 segments (Kapikian *et al.*,2001). *Adenovirus* is belonging to *Adenoviridae* family Group I which are double strand DNA viruses, and the genus *Mastadenovirus*, this genus infects mammalian only (Ghebremedhin,2014). Many human Adenoviruses can replicate in human intestine, but two types of *Adenovirus* 40 and 41 of F subgroups can cause most gastroenteritis in young children (Petric *et al.*, 1999). The virion with icosahedral morphology composed of 252 capsomeres consisting of 240 hexons (Ghebremedhin,2014). *Norovirus* is a member of

the Caliciviridae family which is a single-stranded positive sense RNA virus, non-enveloped virus with icosahedral shaped capsid approximately 27-40 nm in diameter (Adriaenssens *et al.*,2018). Many studies showed that presence of *Norovirus* that mainly come from sewage in water is one of the biggest public health issues in many countries (Schaeffer *et al.*, 2018).

Materials and Methods

One hundred stool samples were collected from children who are suspected to have GE, and their age range was between 27 days to 4 years. These samples were collected from many hospitals and health centers in Wasit province. Fifty stool samples collected from healthy children from two kindergartens as a control group. First, all samples were tested by Rapid Immunochromatographic test (RIT) (CerTestBIOTECS.L./Spain) for *Rotavirus*, *Adenovirus* and *Norovirus* (Fig.1). The stool samples that gave positive result to RIT for *Rotavirus* and 17 samples of control group (negative to RIT for *Rotavirus*) were subjected to RT-qPCR. Their RNAs were extracted using AccZol™ extraction kit (Bioneer, Korea) according to the manufacturer instructions, and the RT-qPCR assay was conducted using specific primers and probe for *Rotavirus A* capsid protein gene, GenBank: X94617.1 (Table 1). On the other hand, DNA was extracted, using AccuPrep® stool DNA Extraction Kit (Bioneer, Korea) according to company instructions, from samples that gave positive result for *Adenovirus* by RIT. The extracted DNA was subjected to real time-qPCR using specific primers and probe for *Adenovirus* capsid gene (hexon gene), GenBank: X51782.1 (Table 1). The primers and probes were designed depend on the National Center for Biotechnology (NCBI)-GenBank database and Primer3 plus program and ordered from Macrogen company, Korea.

Table1. Primers and probes for RT qPCR

Gene	Primer/probe	Sequence	Amplicon size
Rotavirus A capsid protein gene	Forward	TCGTTCCAGTTGATGAGACCAC	74bp
	Revers	TCAAATGGCTGCGCATTGG	

	Probe	FAM- TGACACCAGCGGTAGCAGCA-BHQ-1	
Adenovirus hexon gene Probe	Forward	ACTCCAACAATCGCGATGTG	106bp
	Revers	ATTCTTCCCGCAGCGTTTTG	
	Probe	FAM- GCCTCAAGTGGGGCAGACGC-BHQ-1	

Results and Discussions

Rapid Immunochromatographic Test (RIT)

A hundred stool samples from GE patients and 50 stool samples from healthy children (control group) were collected from hospitals and kindergartens, respectively. The samples were divided into 8 groups (0-2, 3-5, 6-8, 9- 11, 12-17, 18- 23, 24-35, and 36-48 months) with regarding to children's ages according to WHO's recommendations (World Health Organization,

2009) (Table 2). All samples were tested by RIT for *Rotavirus*, *Adenovirus* and *Norovirus*. The results showed that 31samples of GE patients were positive to *Rotavirus* and one sample was positive to *Adenovirus*, while *Norovirus* test showed negative results for all100 samples figure 1. The percentages of viral infections were 31% to *Rotavirus*, 1% to *Adenovirus*, and 0 % to *Norovirus*, while control group RIT results were negative (0 %) for all viruses that were tested in this study (Table 2).

Figure 1. The typical positive result of *Rotavirus* and *Adenovirus*, and negative result for *Norovirus* by RIT

Statistical analysis showed significant differences among viral infection as compared with control group. *Rotavirus* infections were significant

compared to *Adenovirus* infections and also *Rotavirus* infections were significant compared to *Norovirus* infections (Table 2).

Table 2. Distribution of the GE Patients and the Control Group Samples According to Age and Gender

Samples	Age groups (Months)	No.	Males (%)	Females (%)
Patients	0-2	14	8 (57.14)	6(42.85)
	3-5	17	11(64.7)	6(35.29)
	6-8	16	8(50.0)	8(50.0)
	9-11	13	8(61.53)	5(38.46)

	12-17	10	6(60.0)	4(40.0)
	18-23	12	5(41.66)	7(58.33)
	24-35	9	4(44.44)	5(55.55)
	36-48	9	5(55.55)	4(44.44)
	Total (%)	100	56(56)	44(44)
Control group	≤ 48months	50	29(58)	21(42)

Rotavirus was considered as the most important cause of endemic diarrheal illness in infant and young children in worldwide, while *Adenovirus* considered as the second. *Norovirus* was important causes outbreaks of vomiting and diarrheal illness in older children and adults frequently associated with ingestion of (food poisoning) (Jawetz *et al.*, 2016). In this study

all (100) samples were negative to *Norovirus* may be due to the fact that *Norovirus* infections were sporadic in children and adults (Kapikian *et al.*, 2004). Other studies demonstrated that seasonal and geographical differences affect *Norovirus* infection rate, and this may be another reason of negative results of *Norovirus* in this study (Borchardt *et al.*,2004).

Table 3. Results of RIT for *Rotavirus*, *Adenovirus* and *Norovirus* Antigen in Stool Samples of GE Patients and Control Group

Samples	Age groups (Months)	No.	<i>Rotavirus</i> (+ve) No.	Positive %	<i>Adenovirus</i> (+ve) No.	Positive %	<i>Norovirus</i> (+ve) No.
Patients	0-2	14	4	12.9	1	100%	-
	3-5	17	8	25.8	-	-	-
	6-8	16	6	19.35	-	-	-
	9-11	13	5	16.12	-	-	-
	12-17	10	3	9.67	-	-	-
	18-23	12	3	9.67	-	-	-
	24-35	9	1	3.22	-	-	-
	36-48	9	1	3.22	-	-	-
	Total (%)	100	31	-	1	-	0
Control group	≤ 48 months	50	0		0		0
P-value < 0.05 significant							

The result of *Rotavirus* infection percentage was 31% and this is agreed with result of other study done in Iraqi Kurdistan which was 37% (Herish *et al.*,2006), 30% in Baghdad (Abdulrazzaq *et al.*,2009), 33.6% in Basrah (Hassan and Abdul Al-Kader ,2016) and, 33.3 % in Thi-Qar (Lafta *et al.*,2019), and 33.33 % in Mosul (Mohamed *et al.* 2016)and in other country like Italy 35.1% (Biscaro *et al.*,2018). However, this study results disagreed with (Al-Rubaei *et al.*,2013) observed 20 % in Babylon, 53 % in Basrah in 2009 (Mahmood,2015), 40% in Najaf, 51% in Diwaniya (Abood *et al.*,2013). The differences between this study results of *Rotavirus* infections and other studies results might be due to the difference in the strain of the virus, children

susceptibility to infection, nutrition and environmental factors.

While *Adenovirus* infection result was 1% which is in agreement with study in Basrah province, Iraq 2.5 % (Thwiny,2013). Other studies in Iran showed that *Adenovirus* infections ranged between (2.6%-3.3%) in children with age less than 5 years (Modarres *et al.*,2006 ; Kajbaf *et al.*,2013),while in China and Thailand the ratio were 4.7% and 3.6% respectively (Lu *et al.*,2017; Theamboonlers *et al.*,2019), this study result disagreed with (Mahmood,2015) who observed in Baghdad 8% and (Al-Rubaei *et al.*,2013) in Babylon 11% of *Adenovirus* infections. In Italy *Adenovirus* infection rated 1.3 % in 2006-2007 and 3.8% in 2005-2006 (Carraturo *et al.*,2008),

while 1.55 % was in Brazil (Soares *et al*,2008). In this study *Norovirus* infection rate was 0% and this is differ from other studies in Iraq, in Babylon (Al-Rubaei *et al*,2013) observed 16%, in Basrah were 8 % (Thwiny,2013). *Norovirus* detection rate in diarrheal patients was varied from high as 31-48% to as low as 3-5 %, suggesting that the burden of *Norovirus* disease may be highly variable geographically (Borchardt *et al*,2004). The difference among results of this study and the other studies may be belong to many reasons such as; the variation personal community hygiene, geographical and seasonal variations, age of targeted group, type of nutrition, vaccination coverage, and viral strains.

Detection of *Rotavirus* and *Adenovirus* by RT-qPCR

RT-qPCR is the most sensitive and specific method for detection of *Rotavirus* and *Adenovirus* as a causative agent of acute viral gastroenteritis (Strubbia *et al*,2019) used in this study to examine 31 stool samples those gave positive result to RIT for *Rotavirus* and 17 samples of control group (negative to RIT). After extracting RNA for all samples, RT-qPCR was conducted. The results of RT-qPCR were all 31 samples who were RIT positive to *Rotavirus*, were positive to RT-qPCR for *Rotavirus* as well (Fig.2) which represents 31% of all stool sample that been used in this study (Table 3).

Figure 2. RT-qPCR Amplification Log Plot of *Rotavirus* Capsid Gene Shows Positive Results (over threshold line) and Negative Results (under threshold line)

Other study results reported that 36.5 % of their samples were positive to *Rotavirus*, in South West Iran (Ahvaz) (Azaranv *et al*,2016), while another study results found high percentage in Turkey 85.3 % (Durmaz *et al*, 2018), and in Egypt 76.9% (Ibrahim *et al*, 2015). On the other hand the extracted DNA of one sample which gave a

positive result by RIT for *Adenovirus* was subjected to RT-PCR with specific primers and probe for *Adenovirus* capsid gene primer and hexon gene probe. The results showed that the sample, from infant aged (57 days), was positive to *Adenovirus* (Fig.3) , so the result of *Adenovirus* infection was 1%.

Figure 3. RT-qPCR Amplification Log Plot of *Adenovirus* Hexon Gene Shows Positive Result

The result disagreed with (AL-Khafaji *et al*, 2014) in Hilla who mentioned that 9.3 % of their samples were positive for *Adenovirus*; however, other studies reported that the percentage of positive results were 2.25 % in Sudan (Elhaj *et al*,2013). The disagreement may be due to the nutrition, number of samples, environmental factors and genetic factors of virus.

Distributions of *Rotavirus* infections according to age

The results in table (4) showed significant difference in positive *Rotavirus* cases in different age groups and the highest rate (25.8 %) was in the second group 3-5 months; whereas the low rate (3.22 %) was in the last two groups (24-35) and (36-48) months. The result of our study showed a high rate of infection in age group under 2 years (93.54%) which is in agreement with a study conducted by (Al-Rubaei *et al*,2013) in Babylon observed 95% of infection of *Rotavirus* was in children under 2 years, while (Mohamed *et al*,2012) in Mosul showed 30.95%. This study results showed a high rate of *Rotavirus* infection in age group under 2 years and infection rate decreased in age more than 2 years. That may be because acquired immunity or vaccination, vaccination play an important role in in reducing the burden of mortality and

hospitalization in children (Troeger *et al*,2018 ; Costantino *et al*,2018).

Distribution of *Rotavirus* Infections According to Gender

This study results showed that there were no significant differences between male and female in *Rotavirus* infection using RT-qPCR as detection method (Table 4).

Table 4. Distribution of *Rotavirus* Infections Detected by RT-qPCR According to Gender

Gender	No. of patients	No .of Positive for <i>Rotavirus</i>	Prevalence Rate %
Male	56	18	32.14
Female	44	13	29.54
Total	100	31	31
P-value > 0.05		not significant	

These results in the table 4 were agreed with several studies that have been done in different Iraqi provinces, such as but not limit to in Addiwaniya, Najaf, Babylon (Abood *et al*,2013), and Basrah (Thwiny *et al*,2013).

Observations of Clinical Symptoms among *Rotavirus* Patients

The most clinical symptoms that observed among all *Rotavirus* patients in this study were

diarrhoea (100%), vomiting (97.77 %), and fever (61.29%) (Table 5).

Table 5. Clinical Symptoms among Patients Who were Positive to Rotavirus Positive by RT-qPCR

Clinical symptoms	No.of +ve No.=31	Rotavirus +ve %
Diarrhea	31	100
Vomiting	30	97.77
Fever	19	61.29
P- value < 0.05 significant		

Based on the positive RT-qPCR results for Rotavirus infections, the differences between symptoms were significant. Other studies (Thwiny *et al*,2013; Boukougou *et al*,2010) showed similar results to this study result in Basrah and Burkina Faso respectively.

Conclusion

This study found that Rotavirus is the main cause of gastroenteritis (GE) in children in the Wasit province of Iraq. The study used two testing methods (RIT and RT-qPCR) and showed that Rotavirus was most prevalent in males and children aged 3-5 months. While Adenovirus was detected in a small number of cases, Norovirus was not present. The study also confirmed that RT-qPCR is a reliable method for detecting Rotavirus and Adenovirus. The primary symptoms of Rotavirus infection were diarrhea and vomiting. The findings highlight the need for better prevention and control strategies targeting rotavirus in young children in the region.

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